

**SOCIOLINGUISTIC COMPETENCE AS ONE OF THE MAIN
COMPONENTS IN LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE USING
FICTIONAL AUTHENTIC MOVIES**

Israilova Ilona Khalitovna

PhD student of National University

of Uzbekistan named after

Mirzo Ulugbek

ilona1israilova@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7275-4897>

Abstract: *The article is devoted to sociolinguistic competence as one of the important components in learning English through feature films. The article touches upon other components that make up the integrity of communicative competence. The essence and importance of sociolinguistic competence as the main pillar of successful knowledge and functioning of a foreign language is described. The assimilation of this competence is analyzed on the basis of watching authentic films.*

Keywords: *Sociolinguistic competence, communicative competence, discursive competence, strategic competence, grammatical competence*

In professionally oriented communication, a special place is occupied by the ability of an individual to form speech behavior adequately to generally accepted norms of speech communication and, in general, speech activity. Sociolinguistic competence is a component of communicative competence, which in turn includes strategic, grammatical and discursive competence. Wikipedia defines communicative competence as a term in linguistics referring to the grammatical knowledge of a language user in the areas of syntax, morphology, phonology, as well as social knowledge about the correct ways to use statements [1]. According

to Sedov K.F., communicative competence is the ability to build effective speech activity and effective speech behavior that correspond to the norms of social interaction inherent in a particular ethnic group[2] . Tsarenikov D.I. defines communicative competence as a person's ability to communicate in one or all types of speech activity, which is a special quality of a real person acquired in the process of natural communication or specially organized training [3].

Let's briefly touch on the other three components of communicative competence before we proceed to analyze the sociolinguistic one. Grammar competence is a basic knowledge of the language, operating a set of rules and successfully applying them in practice. According to S. Thornbury, grammatical competence is nothing more than the level of mastering the basic code of a language by a person, that is, its grammatical rules, word formation, sentence structure, vocabulary [4]. According to the documents of the Council of Europe, grammatical competence is understood as “knowledge of the grammatical elements of a language and the ability to use them in speech. Grammatical competence includes the ability to understand and express a certain meaning, arranging it in the form of phrases and sentences built according to the rules of a given language (as opposed to the mechanical reproduction of memorized samples) [5].

Thus, grammatical competence is expressed by three main basic levels of language proficiency: phonetic, lexical and grammatical. Possession of the so-called language of the foundations of the three pillars allows you to understand foreign language speech, build functionally correct sentences and communicate with both native speakers and foreign speakers.

Strategic competence is “verbal and non-verbal communication strategies that can be defined as the initiative actions of communication participants in order to create, curtail, resume and redirect communication in various situations [6]. Thanks to strategic competence, the communicant can maintain communication despite possible communication difficulties. Such language techniques come to the rescue: paraphrases, evasive answers, facial expressions, intonation, hesitations,

repetitions, as well as changing the topic and tone of the conversation. The individual is able to cope with the emerging linguistic difficulties through language techniques, thereby masking the imperfection of language knowledge. Strategic competence allows you to build effective communication between communicants without disturbing the course of the discussion.

Discursive competence - includes skills related to the interpretation of messages and the transmission of many types of communication in various settings. A. Davis, A. Brown and C. Elder understand discursive competence as “a component of foreign language communicative competence, which is responsible for the cohesion and coherence of the text [7]”. This is the creation of coherent and coherent texts responsible for an ordered structure. In other words, it is the special knowledge and skills of a communicator necessary for interpreting and creating a structural scheme and linguistic standards of discourse. Discursive competence provides the content of the text with integrity and consistency. The speaker follows the logical plan of the story without straying or changing the topic of the idea, creating an orderly and consistent structure of the message.

And finally, we turn to the topic of our article - sociolinguistic competence. Sociolinguistic competence - the knowledge and skills necessary for the effective use of language in a social context. It is expressed in the norms of politeness, communication registers, linguistic markers of social relations, expressions of folk wisdom [8]. In other words, sociolinguistic competence is the ability to build one's speech behavior in accordance with the communicative goals, intentions, social statuses and roles of communicants in a particular society. Each national-linguo-cultural society has its own norms of communication in society, which can directly oppose other cultures. In this regard, the language should be taught along with the cultural background and not in isolation with learning the necessary rules and words. There should be observation not only of the language but also of the existing contextual background. Different types of sentences and set phrases can be interpreted differently depending on the native language of the foreign speaker.

The ability to maintain rational communication, taking into account the cultural norms of the language being studied. The skills of choosing the right words and expressions, as well as the appropriateness of communicative acts and the naturalness of speech in the presented sociocultural contexts.

The student needs to learn to understand the use of a certain word in a literal or figurative sense. This competence is provided at the genuine level. Feature films, unlike texts, convey emotions, gestures, facial expressions, and even an ironic rhythm. The culture of the language being studied, the norm of communication and behavior are fully displayed. Visually illustrates the behavior of the foreign phone in a given situation. What may be typical for our culture may be unacceptable for a foreigner, just as well as vice versa. The culture of the language being studied directly affects the way and form of constructing sentences. Thus, the English language, in comparison with Russian and Uzbek languages, is the most polite form of constructing statements. These norms have entered the language so much that even in the "tense" atmosphere of the communicative act, they do not lose their syntactic form.

Accordingly, when watching films, sociolinguistic is achieved at an automated level, since the recipient is visually provided with the entire context of the plot with the help of auxiliary tools. In feature films, real everyday situations are modeled and the necessary speech acts are applied in certain situations. The spectator can visually observe various existing everyday situations and the corresponding response to them through natural English phrases and turns.

The culturological approach, being one of the approaches in the implementation of the ideas of student-centered education, has a great influence not only on the construction of the learning process, teaching methods, but also establishes a new style of relationship between a teacher - a student, a student - a group, as a dialogue communication of full-fledged personalities-cultures. According to the theory of intercultural learning, the acquisition of a foreign language means penetration into the individual and collective mentality and culture

of another people and involves acquaintance with the views, assessments and experience of another cultural community, since behind each national language there is a national and cultural specificity of the image of the world, consisting of elements and phenomena inalienable and essential for a given people. Socio-cultural language competence is socio-cultural language knowledge that is adequately used in male-cultural communication. The lack of sociocultural competence skills makes communication much more difficult.

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